

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COOPERATION OF THE TEACHER AND PARENTS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION OF A CHILD

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Abstract. In raising the young generation to be well-behaved, patriotic, and hardworking, it is necessary to pay special attention to their young aspects and character, because without them the goal of education cannot be achieved. The school plays the main role in the upbringing of the young generation, and naturally, this process is carried out together with education. This article discusses the issues of cooperation with parents in the education and upbringing of students.

Keywords: education, training, work, teacher, child, student, cooperation, society, people, parents, form, assembly, family.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the populist policy of independent Uzbekistan, serious changes are taking place every day in the socio-economic, ideological-political, ethnic-cultural life. New factors of the material and spiritual development of our society have an effective effect on the national self-awareness of the people. The democratization and humanization of all aspects of the life of our country are important tasks of restoring the cultural power of our people from a spiritual point of view, ideological renewal and self-realization. Economic, political and legal conditions are being created for the continuous development of secondary schools.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, the content of educational work in our country is aimed at forming a well-rounded generation. Necessary conditions and opportunities have been created in the republic to educate a healthy and mature generation, to bring up the young generation as well-rounded individuals fully meeting the requirements of the 21st century. Documents, programs and plans of state significance have been developed for specific, purposeful implementation of work in this regard. Only - the adoption of the Law on Education to raise a competent generation capable of high general and professional culture, solving promising tasks it is enough to mention the orientation.

Education is an activity aimed at bringing the young generation to adulthood, forming social consciousness and behavior in it, and is aimed at forming mental, physical, moral, and spiritual qualities of a person, in order to ensure that a person lives in society. are the processes of finding the content of the necessary features. Education is aimed at forming a person, and develops on the basis of values that ensure the existence of a person and society.

RESULTS

Education means a set of all influences, activities, actions, and aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring his active participation in social, political, cultural, and educational life. Education is not only the processes carried out in the family, school, children and youth organizations, but also includes the ideology instilled in its leading ideas through mass media, newspapers and magazines. After all, education is a broader concept than education. It provides for the implementation of such education by family and educational institutions and public organizations. In this respect, upbringing is closely related to education.

Good spiritual and moral qualities are formed in a person through education. At this point, it is appropriate to quote the following thoughts of Islam Karimov, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "Of course, education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is an important factor that determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, it forms and enriches the nation's spirituality. is a factor. Therefore, it is impossible to develop spirituality without changing the education system and, on this basis, consciousness. Every parent, teacher, and coach should first of all see a person in the person of each child. Based on this simple requirement, raising our children to be perfect people who have independent and broad thinking skills, who live consciously, should be the main goal and task of the field of education and training.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the above points, it is reasonable to say that it is appropriate to organize educational activities in order to raise the young generation to be patriotic, people-loving, highly spiritual, and to inculcate human qualities.

The main components of the organization of educational work are as follows:

- expression of the goal in specific criteria;
- to serve in the implementation of the purpose of the activity;
- it is important to ensure the management of children's education activities in cooperation with the teacher, parents and the community.

The organization of educational work and increasing its potential, inculcating human qualities in the child's heart depends to a large extent on the organization of the creative activities of educators and students. They arise based on the following factors:

- relationships in the organization of the educational process. In this case, the daily life events of the students are such as motivations about order and behavior in the community and a whole approach to them;

- the purpose, accuracy and effectiveness of educational work.

CONCLUSIONS

Stepping into school is a huge turning point in every child's life. From this period, some limitations come to the most innocent moments of childhood. Now the child in the family has to perform not only some family duties, but also private tasks necessary for his personality. With this, his role in the family does not seem to decrease, but on the contrary, it increases. That is, the period of protecting his reputation not only among family members, but also among society with his personal actions begins.

Currently, there are cases where some parents do not understand the teaching given to their child by the teacher at the school and put various pressures on the school administration and teachers. There are things to tell home even when it is normal. Those who do this have an idea that they want to show off.

When talking about this, parents should first of all look for the mistake in themselves. When a parent wants to think about the future of his child, he should cooperate with the teacher. If, on the contrary, he puts pressure on the teacher, it will affect the general state of the class, and he will not be able to work with other children.

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